

Timely Management of STEMI in a Resource-Limited Setting: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT/INTRODUCTION

The management of ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) in underserved and resource-limited settings presents unique challenges, particularly when advanced facilities like catheterization laboratories are unavailable.^[1] This report details the case of a 58-year-old male presenting with STEMI at a US/MX border hospital, highlighting the critical decision-making and management strategies employed under constrained circumstances.

Keywords: Jaw; Dysphagia; Diaphoresis

CASE PRESENTATION

A 58-year-old man presented to an underserved US/MX border hospital's Emergency Department (ED) at 5:22AM, complaining of a 30 min history of pressing 10/10 chest pain that was radiating to his left arm and jaw. His symptoms were associated with dysphagia, shortness of breath, and diaphoresis that woke him up from his sleep.

The patient had a significant medical history, including Hypertension, Diabetes Type II, and a 40 pack-year history of tobacco, with a progressive decline in cardiac function, evidenced by echocardiograms showing mild left ventricular hypertrophy and reduced ejection fraction.

The patient's presentation was classic for acute coronary syndrome.^[1,2] An immediate ECG confirmed ST elevation in the anterolateral leads, indicative of an anterior wall myocardial infarction (Figure 1).^[2,3]

Management and Outcome

Acetylsalicylic Acid (Aspirin) and nitropaste was administered immediately upon arrival to the ER at 5:22AM.^[4] Heparin infusion was started as soon as the ECG was obtained, and the STEMI was identified.

Because the ER was located >120 min away from the nearest cath lab, TNKase was bolused at 5:34AM after ruling out contraindications.⁶ Atorvastatin 80mg was then given. Because of the unavailability of a cath lab due to prohibitive weather conditions preventing transfer, the cardiologist was called and closely involved. The cardiologist came in, and the patient was started on clopidogrel adhering to STEMI management guidelines.^[1,2,5,6]

Concurrently, antiplatelet therapy, clopidogrel, and continuous ECG monitoring were commenced. Cardiac Markers were measured Elevated cardiac biomarkers were indicated in the patient's profile, confirming that a significant acute cardiac event, a myocardial infarction, had occurred.^[1,2]

30 minutes after the initiation of the TNKase, the patient's vital signs became stable, the chest pain resolved, and the ST segment elevations were observed to be resolving (Figure 2). This swift decision-making led to a significant reduction in the patient's pain and stabilization of his condition.^[5]

After 24 hours, the patient was transferred to a tertiary care center, where cardiac catheterization revealed a lesion in the proximal LAD that required a single DES. He was started on ASA and Plavix. Due to the apical/antero wall akinesis/hypokinesis observed on the echo, apixaban was prescribed for one month to prevent LV thrombus.^[7,8] Post- procedure, the patient's management included optimizing medications for CAD and hypertension, preventing LV thrombus, and implementing lifestyle modifications and preventive measures.^[9] 12 days post-event, the patient followed up at an outpatient cardiology clinic, and reported that he had quit smoking (Figure 3). 3 months post-event, the patient presented to the ED for an unrelated complaint, and his ECG showed complete resolution (Figure 4).

Figure 1:
Title: ECG upon Presentation
Description: ST elevation in the leads V2-6 with reciprocal changes in I and AVL.

Figure 2:
Title: Patient's ECG 30 minutes later
Description: Normal sinus rhythm, ST elevations V2-3, T wave inversions I/aVL/V2-V6, Qwaves aVL, V2-V3.

Figure 3:
Title: Patient's ECG from outpatient cardiology clinic 12 days post-event
Description: ECG revealed T wave inversions. These findings were consistent with the recent anterior myocardial infarction. No new acute ischemic changes were present, suggesting stabilization of the post-MI state.

Figure 4:
Title: Patient's ECG 3 months post-event
Description: Normalized ECG

DISCUSSION

This case exemplifies the critical importance of rapid decision-making and resourcefulness in STEMI management, particularly in settings lacking full cardiac intervention facilities.^[5,6,10] The prompt use of fibrinolytic therapy in the face of logistical challenges likely prevented significant myocardial damage and improved the patient's outcome.^[1,6,9,11] This finding is important to reiterate since, according to the US National Registry, despite recommendations, only 46% of patients receiving fibrinolytic therapy were treated within the recommended 30-minute door-to-needle time, with no significant improvement in this metric over four years.¹² It also underscores the necessity of comprehensive, continuous care – from initial presentation through long-term management – in patients with complex cardiac presentations.^[7,8,9]

Furthermore, this case highlights the disparities in healthcare accessibility and the need for adaptable protocols in underserved areas.^[13] The successful management in this case serves as a model for similar scenarios, demonstrating that quality care can be delivered, especially in resource-limited settings.^[13,14,15]

CONCLUSION

The effective management of STEMI in a resource-limited setting requires not only adherence to established guidelines but also the ability to make rapid, informed decisions under pressure. This case demonstrates that with the right approach, even challenging scenarios in underserved areas can result in successful outcomes, emphasizing the importance of preparedness, adaptability, and comprehensive care in cardiology.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

Approval from ethics committee not required. All procedures were performed in compliance with relevant laws and institutional guidelines. The patient gives full informed consent to the publication of this case report.

DECLARATIONS OF INTEREST

None

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REFERENCES

1. O’Gara PT, Kushner FG, Ascheim DD, Casey DE, Chung MK, De Lemos JA, et al. 2013 ACCF/AHA Guideline for the Management of ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2013;61(4):e78–140.
2. Six AJ, Backus BE, Kelder JC. Chest pain in the emergency room: value of the HEART score. Neth Heart J. 2008;16(6):191–6.
3. Nikus K, Pahlm O, Wagner G, Birnbaum Y, Cinca J, Clemmensen P, et al. Electrocardiographic classification of acute coronary syndromes: a review by a committee of the International Society for Holter and Non-Invasive Electrocardiology. J Electrocardiol. 2010;43(2):91–103.
4. Mehta RH, Criger DA, Granger CB, Pieper KK, Califf RM, Topol EJ, et al. Patient outcomes after fibrinolytic therapy for acute myocardial infarction at hospitals with and without coronary revascularization capability. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2002;40(6):1034–40.
5. Ron Walls, Robert Hockberger, Marianne Gausche-Hill, Timothy B. Erickson, Susan R. Wilcox. Rosen’s Emergency Medicine: Concepts and Clinical Practice. 10th ed. 2022.
6. Initial evaluation and management of suspected acute coronary syndrome (myocardial infarction, unstable angina) in the emergency department – UpToDate.
7. Bennett S, Satchithananda D. The use of Apixaban for the treatment of an LV thrombus. Echo Res Pract. 2018;5(4):K63–6.
8. Alcalai R, Rashad R, Butnaru A, Moravsky G, Leibowitz D. Apixaban versus Warfarin in Patients with Left Ventricular (LV) Thrombus, a prospective randomized trial. Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Pharmacother. 2022;8(7):660-667.
9. Fox KAA, Dabbous OH, Goldberg RJ, Pieper KS, Eagle KA, Werf FV de, et al. Prediction of risk of death and myocardial infarction in the six months after presentation with acute coronary syndrome: prospective multinational observational study (GRACE). BMJ. 2006;333(7578):1091.
10. McCord J, Cabrera R, Lindahl B, Giannitsis E, Evans K, Nowak R, et al. Prognostic Utility of a Modified HEART Score in Chest Pain Patients in the Emergency Department. Circ Cardiovasc Qual Outcomes. 2017;10(2):e003101.
11. Cenko E, Ricci B, Kedev S, Vasiljevic Z, Dorobantu M, Gustiene O, et al. Reperfusion therapy for ST-

- elevation acute myocardial infarction in Eastern Europe: the ISACS-TC registry. Eur Heart J - Qual Care Clin Outcomes. 2016;2(1):45–51.
12. McNamara RL, Herrin J, Bradley EH, Portnay EL, Curtis JP, Wang Y, et al. Hospital Improvement in Time to Reperfusion in Patients With Acute Myocardial Infarction, 1999 to 2002. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2006;47(1):45–51.
 13. Vanzella LM, Pakosh M, Oh P, Ghisi G. Health-related information needs and preferences for information of individuals with cardiovascular disease from underserved populations: A systematic review. Patient Educ Couns. 2022;105(12):3398–409.
 14. Moser DK, Kimble LP, Alberts MJ, Alonzo A, Croft JB, Dracup K, et al. Reducing Delay in Seeking Treatment by Patients With Acute Coronary Syndrome and Stroke. Circulation. 2006;114(2):168–82.
 15. Rashid M, Fischman DL, Martinez SC, Capers Q, Savage M, Zaman A, et al. Temporal trends and predictors of time to coronary angiography following non-ST-elevation acute coronary syndrome in the USA. Coron Artery Dis. 2019;30(3):159–70.